

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS ANALYSIS OF A CRACKED CYLINDRICAL SHELL BONDED WITH A COMPOSITE PATCH

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ABSTRACT: Adhesively bonded repair has been used as an efficient and economical method to extend the service life of cracked structural components. Most of the currently available analysis methods and empirical databases for composite bonded repair to flat structures are computationally efficient and easy to use. However, the current knowledge on composite bonded repair for flat structures cannot be directly applied to curved repairs. In this paper, a novel adhesive element developed by the authors in conjunction with a shell element is employed to investigate the fracture toughness at the crack tip of a cracked cylindrical shell bonded with a composite patch. To validate of the present finite element model for curved composite patch repair, the stress intensity factors in a flat composite repair are firstly computed and compared with those available in the literature. For the curved repairs, a full 3-D finite element analysis is also conducted to validate the proposed numerical model. Some numerical examples are given to demonstrate the effect of curvature on the fracture toughness of curved patch repairs.

KEYWORDS: composite patch repair, adhesive bonding, bonded repair, fracture toughness, thin-walled structure

1. INTRODUCTION

Damage can occur in the form of a delamination or crack during manufacturing and/or service for most load-carry structures. The challenging problem is how to repair these damaged structures to achieve the original designated service life. The application of an adhesively bonded composite patch to repair a cracked thin-wall structure is widely used in aging aircraft because of its high structural efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

A large amount of scientific research work on designing and assessing composite repairs has been published since the early 1970s [1-5]. One of the most challenging aspects of bonded composite repair technology is to develop an accurate tool for investigating the fracture toughness in the cracked structures after repair. Because of the difficulty in producing an analytical solution for the composite patch repair, most research work employs the numerical methods to analyze the stress field at the crack tip, such as full 3-D FEA [6-8], 2-D FEA [9, 10], boundary element method [11], etc. These currently available analysis methods and empirical databases are computationally efficient and easy to use for composite patch repair to flat structures. However, curved thin-walled structures are also widely used in engineering applications, such as aircraft wing skin, fuselage, etc., and the current knowledge on composite bonded repairs for flat structures cannot be directly applied to those curved repairs. Therefore, it is necessary to study the curved repairs for better understanding of the effect of curvature on repair effectiveness.

The authors proposed a curved adhesive element formulation [12], combined with plate/shell elements, to analyze the stress in the bond line of a curved bonded joint. In this paper, an adhesive element in conjunction with a Serendipity degenerated shell element [13] is employed to investigate the effect of

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curvature on fracture toughness of the curved composite patch repairs. The stress intensity factors in a flat composite repair are firstly computed using the present finite element model and compared with those available in the literature. For the curved repairs, a full 3-D finite element analysis is also conducted to validate the proposed numerical model.

Figure 1 A cracked cylindrical shell with a bonded composite patch

2. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Figure 1, shows a cylindrical metallic shell with an embedded through-thickness central crack, over which is bonded a single-sided composite patch. The overlap region can be modeled by using the developed scheme [12], in which both the shell and the patch are modeled using shell elements and the adhesive layer is modeled by using pseudo brick elements. The shell and patch are simulated by 8-noded Serendipity degenerated shell elements considering the shear deformation and the linear displacement field is given by [13]

$$U(x, y, z) = u^0(x, y) + z\theta_y(x, y), \quad V(x, y, z) = v^0(x, y) - z\theta_x(x, y), \quad W(x, y, z) = w(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where u, v, w are the translational displacements, and θ_x, θ_y are the rotations of the directional normal about x and y coordinate respectively. The superscript ⁰ denotes the mid-plane of shell elements, which sandwiches the adhesive layer.

Accordingly, the adhesive layer is modeled by a 16-noded adhesive element [12]. The patch is assumed to be perfectly bonded to the curved surface with uniform thickness and no debonding occurs in the entire adhesive layer. The thickness of adhesive layer is very thin compared to that of patch and curved surface. Therefore the strains in the adhesive layer are assumed to be constant across the thickness of the adhesive layer. Only three out-of-plane stresses $\sigma_z, \gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{xz}$ are considered for the adhesive layer. Following these three assumptions, the three constant adhesive stains can be readily obtained as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{zz}^A &= (w_i - w_j) / t \\ \gamma_{yz}^A &= (v_i - v_j) / t = (v_i^0 - v_j^0 + \theta_{xi} \cdot H_u / 2 + \theta_{xj} \cdot H_l / 2) / t \\ \gamma_{xz}^A &= (u_i - u_j) / t = (u_i^0 - u_j^0 - \theta_{yi} \cdot H_u / 2 - \theta_{yj} \cdot H_l / 2) / t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts i and j denote the corresponding upper and lower shell elements, respectively. H_u and H_l represent the thickness of the upper and lower shell elements, namely, the thickness of the host shell and the bonded composite patch, respectively. t is the thickness of the adhesive layer.

3. FRACTURE TOUGHNESS ANALYSIS

3.1 Strain energy release rate (SERR)

In this paper, only Mode I fracture loading is considered. The virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [14] is employed to compute the Mode I strain energy release rate. It should be noted that the same procedure can also be used for mixed mode loading and for the computation of the mixed mode SERR.

Figure 2 shows a finite element mesh near the crack tip at point c , where the crack is assumed to be enclosed by a small length of Δa . The closure forces needed at point a and b are taken to be the same as those at point c and d , respectively. Thus, the strain energy release rate can be calculated as the work done by the nodal force (moment) F_{cy} , F_{dy} (M_{cx} , M_{dx}), in closing the crack opening displacement (rotation) v_{ay}^0 , v_{by}^0 (θ_{ax} , θ_{bx}). The total strain energy release rate is obtained as

$$G_{\text{TOTAL}} = G_u + G_\phi \quad (3)$$

where

$$G_u = \frac{1}{2\Delta a \cdot H} [F_{cy}(v_{ay}^0 - v_{a'y}^0) + F_{dy}(v_{by}^0 - v_{b'y}^0)]$$

$$G_\phi = \frac{1}{2\Delta a \cdot H} [M_{cx}(\theta_{ax} - \theta_{a'x}) + M_{dx}(\theta_{bx} - \theta_{b'x})] \quad (4)$$

where H is the crack thickness.

3.2 Stress intensity factor

To compare the current analysis results with those in the literature, stress intensity factor is also calculated from the SERR obtained from (3) and (4). According to Yong and Sun [15], if the rotational (bending) contribution to the strain energy release rate G_ϕ is small, Mode I stress intensity factor in the state of plane stress can be obtained by

$$K_I = K_u = \sqrt{G_u E_s} \quad (5)$$

where the subscript s denotes parameters associated with the host cylindrical shell.

If bending is not negligible, then stress intensity factor for pure bending moments under the state of plane stress can be given by

$$K_\phi = \sqrt{3G_\phi E_s} \quad (6)$$

Figure 2 Crack tip elements (top view)

Subsequently, the maximum stress intensity factor over the thickness of the plate is

$$K_I = K_u + K_\phi \quad (7)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To verify the present finite element model for curved composite patch repair, the stress intensity factors in both flat and curved composite patch repair are computed and compared with those available in the literature and/or 3-D finite element solutions.

4.1 Single-sided composite patch bonded to a cracked flat plate

As shown in Figure 3, a center-cracked aluminum plate, which is adhesively bonded with a boron composite patch on one side, has been investigated in previous studies [8-10]. The material properties and dimensions of the single-sided repair are given in Table 1, which are the same as those employed in previous studies. The total length of the central crack is $2a = 50.0\text{mm}$. Due to the structural symmetry, only a quarter of the single-sided repair is modeled.

Figure 3 Single-sided composite patch bonded to a cracked flat plate

Three load cases are considered in the calculation of the stress intensity factors by assuming that the local stress field near the crack tip is in a state of plane strain, which leads to the relationship between the SERR and the stress intensity factor as

$$K_I = \sqrt{\frac{GE}{(1-\nu^2)}} \quad (8)$$

where ν is the Poisson's ratio of the cylindrical shell.

The three load cases are $\lambda=-2$, $\lambda=0$, and $\lambda=2$, where the biaxial load factor λ is defined as

$$\lambda = \sigma_x / \sigma_y \quad (9)$$

The stress intensity factors are normalized with respect to $\sigma_y \sqrt{\pi a}$, i.e. the normalized value for the stress intensity factor is

$$K = \frac{K_I}{\sigma_y \sqrt{\pi a}} \quad (10)$$

Table 1 Material properties and dimensions of a single-sided flat repair

Layer	Length L (mm)	Width W (mm)	Thickness H (mm)	Material properties
Aluminum plate	180.0	120.0	2.2900	$E=71.02$ GPa, $\nu=0.32$
Adhesive	76.0	38.0	0.1016	$E=0.965$ GPa, $\nu=0.32$
Composite patch	76.0	38.0	0.7620	$E_1=208$ GPa, $E_2=E_3=25.44$ GPa $G_{23}=4.94$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=7.24$ GPa $\nu_{23}=0.035$, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.1677$

Table 2 Comparison of K^m at the mid-plane for single-sided flat repair

λ	K^m				
	Present	Chue et al. 3-D [8]	Sun et al. 2-D plate model [9]	Naboulsi et al. three layer technique [10]	Sun et al. 3-D [9]
-2	0.555	0.392	0.493	0.552	0.565
0	0.607	0.481	0.536	0.570	0.612
2	0.658	0.571	0.579	0.609	0.660

Table 3 Comparison of K^f at the free surface for single-sided flat repair

λ	K^f				
	Present	Chue et al. 3-D [8]	Sun et al. 2-D plate model [9]	Naboulsi et al. three layer technique [10]	Sun et al. 3-D [9]
-2	0.992	0.742	0.900	0.945	0.933
0	1.050	0.902	0.953	0.982	0.985
2	1.108	1.062	1.007	1.019	1.036

This problem has been investigated by Chue et al. [8], Sun et al. [9], using 3-D finite element analysis, and also by Sun et al. [9] and Naboulsi et al. [10] using Mindlin plate theory and the three layer technique, respectively. The 3-D finite element solutions show that the stress intensity factor through the plate thickness is nearly linear, which supports the use of plate/shell elements that assume a linear distribution of bending stress over the plate thickness [9]. Therefore, comparisons of the single-sided composite repairs stress intensity factor are made at the plate mid-plane and free edge. Tables 2 and 3 list the normalized stress intensity factors at the mid-plane, K^m , and at the free surface of the plate, K^f .

The 3-D finite element solutions in [8] and [9] are obtained using two and more layers of 20-noded brick element across the aluminum plate thickness and the later model is more refined. The present stress intensity factors at both the mid-plane and the free surface are in a very good agreement with those from Sun et al's 3-D model [9], especially for the results at the mid-plane with the difference being less than 2%. For the stress intensity factors at the free surface, the maximum difference is 7%. Further, the present results at the mid-plane are in better agreement with 3-D finite element solutions than those from Mindlin plate theory [9] and the three layer technique [10] because of the use of a more accurate 8-node element, while 4-node elements are used in the later two analyses. This clearly shows the validity and advantage of the present finite element model in the analysis of flat composite patch repair.

4.2 Single-sided composite patch bonded to a cracked cylindrical shell

As shown in Figure 1, a center-cracked cylindrical shell, which is adhesively bonded with a boron composite patch at its outer surface, is considered. The material properties and dimensions of the single-sided curved repair are given in Table 4. The total length of the central crack is $2a = 15.0$ mm. Only a

quarter of the single-sided repair is modeled due to the structural symmetry. The three biaxial load cases are $\lambda=-2$, $\lambda=0$, and $\lambda=2$, where λ is defined in Section 4.1. Similar to Section 4.1, the stress intensity factors are calculated by assuming that the local stress field near the crack tip is in a state of plane strain and normalized using equation (10). Table 5 lists the normalized stress intensity factors at the mid-plane, K^m , and at the free surface of the cylindrical shell, K^f . These are obtained using 3-D finite element analysis and the present finite element model, respectively.

Table 4 Material properties and dimensions of a single-sided curved repair

Layer	Sector angle α (mm)	Width W (mm)	Thickness H (mm)	Material properties
Aluminum shell	30.0	30.0	1.0	$E=70.0$ GPa, $\nu=0.30$
Adhesive	15.0	15.0	0.15	$E=2.4$ GPa, $\nu=0.30$
Composite patch	15.0	15.0	1.0	$E_1=208$ GPa, $E_2=E_3=25.44$ GPa $G_{23}=4.94$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=7.24$ GPa $\nu_{23}=0.035$, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.1677$
Radius of the outer surface of the shell is $R=100.0$ mm				

Table 5 Comparison of K^m and K^f for single-sided curved repair

λ	K^m			K^f		
	Present (K)	3-D (K_0)	$(K-K_0)/K_0$ (%)	Present (K)	3-D (K_0)	$(K-K_0)/K_0$ (%)
-2	11.165	11.219	-0.5	17.193	15.821	8.7
0	11.120	11.130	-0.1	17.095	15.686	9.0
2	11.074	10.992	0.7	16.997	15.552	9.3

Figure 4 Distribution of normalized stress intensity factor through-the-thickness of cylindrical shell ($\lambda=0$) for single-sided repair

A commercial finite element analysis software called STRAND7 [16] is used to conduct a 3-D finite element analysis of a curved composite patch repair. For the 3-D finite element model, 9 layers and 2 layers of 8-node brick elements are employed for the cylindrical shell and the bonded patch, respectively.

As a convergence analysis, 1, 2 and 4 layers of brick element are used for the adhesive layer, which shows that one layer of brick elements can provide enough accuracy for the stress intensity factors. This is also testified by reference [6] for the flat repair. The results in Table 5 are obtained by a 4 layers of brick elements in the adhesive layer.

From Table 5, it can be seen that the stress intensity factors at the mid-plane obtained by the present shell element model correlate very well to those calculated by 3-D finite element model with the maximum difference less than 1%. However, similar to the case of flat repair in section 4.1, a larger difference is noted for the stress intensity factors at the free surface with the maximum difference 9.3% for $\lambda = 2$. There are three reasons that may cause stress intensity factors between 3-D and present finite element models being different. The first is the difference in the simulation of the adhesive layer. Only three out-of-plane stresses in the bonding line are considered in the present model, while all six stress components are taken into account in the 3-D FE model. Secondly, the distribution of the stress intensity factors through-the-thickness of the cylindrical shell is different for the two models. For the present shell model, the Mode I stress intensity factor is linearly distributed through the cylindrical shell thickness. However, the 3-D FEA shows that this distribution is nearly linear, which is depicted in Figure 4 with the zero position at the adhesive-cylindrical shell interface. It should be noted that the difference in the stress intensity factors between that at the mid-plane and that at the free surface is contributed to the bending moment at the crack plane. It is apparent that the bending moment for the curved repairs is much larger than that for the flat repairs with the same load case and boundary conditions stated in Section 4.1. Therefore, the error in K^f for the curved repairs predicted by the present shell model should be slightly higher than that for the flat repairs. The last possible reason is that the crack closure, caused by the bending moment, is not considered in the present model. Although the crack closure is not found in the present numerical examples from 3-D FEA, i.e., $K^f - K^m < K^m$, it is worth being pointed out that the crack closure may produce some differences between the two models.

Table 5 shows that the present shell model can effectively and efficiently analyze curved patch repairs.

4.3 Single-sided curved composite patch repairs subject to tensile loads

Consider the same configuration of curved bonded repair as that in Section 4.2. Only tensile loads in the y-direction are applied to both ends of the cylindrical shell. Two cases are analyzed, i.e., keeping the span ($R\sin\alpha_s = 50.0\text{mm}$) or the height ($R(1 - \cos\alpha_s) = 13.4\text{mm}$) of the cylindrical shell constant, respectively. The constant length of the bonded patch is 26.18mm. The crack length is $2a = 15.0\text{mm}$. The other structure dimensions and material properties are the same as those in Section 4.2.

Figure 5 depicts the stress intensity factors, which are normalized using equation (10), for different radius of cylindrical shell and for both cases. When the height of the cylindrical shell is kept constant, both the bending moment M_x and membrane force F_y are nearly constant at the crack plane. It can be seen from Figure 5 that both the stress intensity factors, at the mid-plane and at the free surface of the cylindrical shell, increase slightly with larger curvature, $1/R$. Whilst the comparison of the stress intensity factor contributed by the bending moment, $K^f - K^m$, indicates that larger a curvature can also result in an increase in the pure bending stress intensity factor. When the span of the cylindrical shell is kept constant, only the membrane force F_y is constant at the crack plane, while the bending moment at the crack plane will increase for the larger curvature. From Figure 5, it is evident that the larger bending moment at the crack plane can lead not only to a significant increase in K^m , but also a substantial increase in K^f . Moreover, it also results in a considerable increase in the pure bending stress intensity factor, $K^f - K^m$. It is, therefore, very important to consider the effect of curvature and loading case in designing curved patch repairs.

Figure 5 Normalized stress intensity factors of single-sided curved composite patch repairs subject to tensile loads

Figure 6 Normalized stress intensity factors of single-sided curved composite patch repairs subject to bending moments

4.4 Single-sided curved composite patch repairs subject to a bending moment

To further identify the effect of curvature on fracture toughness of the curved patch repair, a composite patch repair subject to a constant bending moment is considered. As shown in Figure 1, the arc length of bonded patch and the cylindrical shell are kept constant at 25.0mm and 50.0mm, respectively. A pair of uniform bending moments about the x -axis, $m_x=1.0\text{N}$, is applied to both ends of the bonded repair. The crack length is $2a=15.0\text{mm}$. The other structure dimensions and the material properties are the same as those in Section 4.2. The stress intensity factors are normalized by

$$K = \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{\pi a}} \quad (11)$$

Figure 6 depicts the normalized stress intensity factors at the mid-plane and at the free surface for different radii of cylindrical shell. It can be seen that the stress intensity factors at the mid-plane and at the free surface of the cylindrical shell are increased by 40% and 39% when the curvature of the cylindrical shell varies from 0 (flat) to 0.01. This difference indicates that the effect of curvature must be considered in designing curved patch repairs.

5. CONCLUSION

A finite element model is proposed in this paper to investigate the fracture toughness of the cracked cylindrical shell repaired by a single-sided bonded composite patch. The comparison of the numerical results between those obtained by the present model and those available in the literature or 3-D finite element analysis shows that the present numerical model has a high level of accuracy in the predication of stress intensity factor at the mid-plane of the cylindrical shell. The maximum stress intensity factor at the crack tip predicted by the present model is higher than that obtained by 3-D finite element analysis. Selected parametric results show that an increase in curvature of the cylindrical shell may lead to a higher stress intensity factor under the same repair configuration. Further results will be presented to fully understand the effect of curvature on the effectiveness of composite patch repairs.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Baker AA, Repair of cracked or defected metallic aircraft components with advanced fibre composites—an overview of Australian work, *Composite Structures*, 1984; 2:153-81.
- [2] Baker AA and Jones R. *Bonded repair of aircraft structures*. Martinus Nijhoff: Dordrecht; 1988.
- [3] Hart-Smith LJ, *The design of repairable advanced composite structures*, Douglas Paper 7550, McDonnell Douglas, Douglas Aircraft Company, 1985.
- [4] Adams R D Comyn J and Wake WC, *Structural Adhesive Joints in Engineering*, 2nd Edition, Chapman & Hall: London; 1997.
- [5] Tong L and Steven GP, *Analysis and Design of Structural Bonded Joints*, Kluwer Academic Publishers: Boston; 1999.
- [6] Umamaheswar T VRS, Singh R, Modeling of a patch repair to a thin cracked sheet, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 1999; 62:267-289.

- [7] Bouiadjra BB, Belhouari M and Serier B, Computation of the stress intensity factors for repaired cracks with bonded composite patch in mode I and mixed mode, *Composite Structures*, 2002; 56:401-406.
- [8] Chue CH, Chang LC, Tsai JS, Bonded repair of a plate with inclined central crack under biaxial loading, *Composite Structures*, 1994; 28:39-45.
- [9] Sun CT, Klug J, Arendt C, Analysis of cracked plates repaired with bonded composite patches, *AIAA Journal*, 1996; 34:369-74.
- [10] Naboulsi S, Mall S, Modeling of a cracked metallic structure with bonded composite patch using the three layer technique, *Composite Structures*, 1996; 35:295-308.
- [11] Young A, Rooke DP and Cartwright DJ, Analysis of patched and stiffened cracked panels using the boundary element method, *International Journal of Solid Structures*, 1992; 29:2201-2216.
- [12] Tong L and Sun X, Adhesive elements for stress analysis of bonded patch to curved thin-walled structures, *Computational Mechanics*, 2003; 30:143-154.
- [13] Zienkiewicz O C and Taylor R L, *The Finite Element Method*. 4th Ed. Vol. 1 Basic Formulation and Linear Problems. McGraw-Hill Book Company: London; 1989.
- [14] Rybicki, EF and Kanninen EF, A finite element calculation of stress intensity factors by a modified crack closure integral, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 1977; 9: 931-938.
- [15] Young MJ and Sun CT, On the strain energy release rate for a cracked plate subjected to out-of-plane bending moment, *International Journal of fracture*, 1993; 60:227-247.
- [16] G+D Computing Pty Ltd., Using Strand 7 – Introduction to the Strand7 Finite Element Analysis System, Sydney, Australia, Edition 1, May 1999 (ISBN 0-646-37288-2).